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An Assessment of Renewable Energy Policies in Nigeria: Challenges and Opportunities

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the Nigeria Energy and natural resource policy using a systematic scoping review. Information and materials were obtained from secondary sources such as journal articles, books, and other online resources, spanning quantitative, qualitative, and review studies, and covering the period from 2000 to 2025. Several search engines, including Google Scholar, RefSeek, and others, were used during the search process, and the information retrieved was subjected to content and thematic analysis. The findings revealed that the Nigeria Energy and natural resource policy has a direct effect on the propensity of achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. However, several challenges hinder the effective use of renewable energy policy. These include regulatory bottlenecks, inadequate application of policy to transform the renewable energy system. It was recommended among others that there is the need for proper legislation and enforcement procedure through the machinery of the law, the government and policymakers should establish a clear and comprehensive policy and regulatory framework to support the development of energy and renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal energy. The government should increase Nigeria's energy targets and ambitions to unlock low-carbon growth and align with global climate and sustainable development objectives. There is a need to invest in renewable energy infrastructure, including transmission and distribution networks, to facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources into the national grid. The government and policymakers should enhance public awareness and education on the benefits of renewable energy to promote adoption and increase support for renewable energy policies.

Keywords: Energy, Policy, Nigerian Energy, National Policy, Sources of Energy

INTRODUCTION

Energy forms the bedrock of all modern human activities and is a key prerequisite for the development of any country. This is evident by the influence a country's energy policy has on its socio-economic developments, and vice versa (Lee 2006). In a nutshell, energy policy typically includes a government's specific strategy to explore, exploit, manage and preserve its diverse energy resources, and portfolio to primarily satisfy its local energy demands. Given the implication of various stages of exploiting energy resources on the environment, national energy policy should also include environmental conservation, for sustainable development. Therefore, feasibility analysis of an energy policy is admittedly sensitive to regional and temporal parameters. Nigeria is the most populous African nation - with current population estimates of about 180 million from last official census (National Population Commission 2006)). The country is also one of the largest economies in Africa (Shapshak 2016), rich in natural resources, yet its development is hindered by persistent energy crisis. By 'energy crisis', we refer to regular encountered power outages and below-par energy infrastructures, with between 60 – 70 % of the population lacking access to electricity as at 2012 (Oyedepo 2012). As the largest oil producer in Africa and one of the leading OPEC countries, oil and gas is inevitably the country's prime energy option, with studies showing that most of its energy has been historically supplied by fossil fuels and biomass (World Data Bank 2018). A prevalent energy crisis in Nigeria therefore points to poor management of the vastly available energy resources and/or a faulty energy policy.

To address this issue, several previous works have evaluated the potentials of major oil & gas (Abam et al. 2014; Emodi et al. 2017; Nelson 2015; Ogunlowo, Bristow, and Sohail 2015) and renewable (Aliyu, Dada, and Adam 2015; Gana and Hoppe 2017; Mas'ud et al. 2015; Shaaban and Petinrin 2014) energy resources in Nigeria. These and more studies (like (Oyedepo 2014)) attempted to influence policy and policy makers to adopt policy recommendations which will see the country energy subsistent in an environmentally sustainable manner.

However, many of the policy recommendations go largely unacknowledged. Even when they are adopted in policies at various levels of governmental regulation, there is an absence of a quality check to act as a score card for the potency of policy implementation or the national energy policy. This quality-check is the main aim of the present study. Herein, following a summary of energy resources and energy supply status quo in Nigeria, we evaluate the potency of Nigerian national energy policy so far under; economic impact, environmental impact and domestic delivery/accessibility targets, before making policy

recommendations. The two major national policy documents the present study focuses on are the Nigerian; ‘National Energy Policy’ (NEP) (Energy Commission of Nigeria 2003) and the ‘National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy’ (NREEP) (Ministry of Power 2015). This work reviews provisions in these two documents and their adaptation in relevant government ministries; by highlighting areas of strength and exposing inadequacies to present and future policy makers in the country.

Statement of the problem

Nigeria's over-reliance on fossil fuels has resulted in persistent energy shortages, environmental degradation, and economic challenges, despite the country's abundant renewable energy resources. The lack of effective renewable energy policies and implementation frameworks has hindered the development and utilization of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, thereby exacerbating energy poverty and undermining sustainable development. Furthermore, inadequate policy frameworks, limited institutional capacity, insufficient funding, and lack of public awareness and education on renewable energy benefits have all contributed to the slow pace of renewable energy development in Nigeria. As a result, the country is missing out on opportunities to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions, improve energy security, and promote sustainable economic growth, underscoring the need for a comprehensive assessment of renewable energy policies in Nigeria to identify challenges and opportunities for promoting sustainable energy development.

Aim and objectives of the problem

The main aim of this study is to assess renewable energy policies in Nigeria: challenges and opportunities. The specific objectives of the study include:

1. Examine the status and sources of energy use in Nigeria.
2. Investigate the need for a national energy policy.
3. Evaluate energy security challenges in Nigeria.
4. Examine the challenges of renewable energy policy on sustainable development.
5. Investigate the theoretical underpinning of the administration of energy resources and systems.

Research questions

The following research questions give credence to the study

1. What is the status and sources of energy use in Nigeria?
2. What is the need for a National energy policy?
3. What are the energy security challenges in Nigeria?
4. What are the challenges of renewable energy policy on sustainable development?
5. In what ways can theories be applied to address the challenges of the administration of energy resources and systems?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it:

1. **Contributes to policy development:** By assessing renewable energy policies in Nigeria, this study can inform policy decisions and contribute to the development of effective frameworks for promoting sustainable energy development.
2. **Provides a comprehensive review:** The study's examination of existing literature and policies can provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with renewable energy development in Nigeria.
3. **Supports sustainable development:** By identifying strategies for promoting renewable energy development, this study can contribute to Nigeria's sustainable development goals, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving energy security.
4. **Informs stakeholders:** The study's findings can inform stakeholders, including policymakers, industry players, and civil society organizations, on the need for effective renewable energy policies and strategies.

Limitations of the Study

This study has the following limitations:

1. **Theoretical analysis only:** The study does not involve empirical data analysis, which may limit the depth of understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with renewable energy development in Nigeria.

2. Literature-based analysis: The study's findings are based on existing literature and policies, which may not reflect the current situation on the ground.
3. Limited scope: The study focuses on renewable energy policies in Nigeria, which may not be generalizable to other countries or contexts.
4. Potential bias: The study's findings may be influenced by the researcher's interpretation of existing literature and policies.

These limitations highlight the need for future studies to build on this research and provide more comprehensive insights into renewable energy development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Status and Sources of Energy Use in Nigeria.

Energy is the most fundamental part of our universe, it lights our cities, power our vehicles, transport planes and rockets, warms our homes, cook our food, play our music and powers machinery in factories. Energy drives development and sustains economic systems. Civilization gets the energy it needs from energy resources such as fossil fuels, nuclear fuel and renewable energy (Somorin et al 2019). The available energy resources in Nigeria range from hydrocarbons such as oil, gas, coal and uranium, to renewable energy such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, biomass and geothermal as well as the potential to develop nuclear energy as an alternative source of electricity. All forms of energy are stored in different ways, in the energy sources that we use every day. We can divide these sources of energy into two major groups:

Renewable energy is an energy source that we can use and replenish. We cannot exhaust or run out of renewable energy because we can renew as we use. Examples of sources of renewable energy are sun (solar energy), wind (wind energy), earth (geothermal energy), biological waste (biomass energy), and water (hydropower). Solar energy, from the sun, is turned into heat and electricity so also the other forms of renewable energy. Non-renewable energy: this is the conventional source of energy, which we cannot replace as we use - it cannot be renewed.

As argued by Somorin et al (2019), Non- renewable sources include fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas and coal. They are called fossil fuels because they were formed over millions and millions of years by the action of heat from the Earth's core and pressure from rock and soil on the remains (or "fossils") of dead plants and animals. Another non-renewable energy source is the element uranium, whose atoms we split (through a process called nuclear fission) to create heat and ultimately electricity. The major source of energy use in Nigeria is non- renewable. Oil is found in form of large deposits of crude in the Niger Delta while natural gas is found alongside the oil. Nigeria's energy use is dominated by oil to the neglect of the other resources. Large deposits of oil in crude form are found in abundance in Nigeria as she is rated as having a large deposit of natural gas with some oil in it. This is because her abundant reserves of natural gas are estimated to be more than 100 trillion standard cubic feet, and this is far in excess of the crude oil reserves of the country -this is enough to see Nigeria through two hundred years of domestic consumption and export. Nigeria is currently not focusing much on the gas reserves even though she possesses this in abundance (Somorin et al 2019). Nigeria is likely to become a major gas rather than oil producer if all the potentials are fully developed. A very large quantity of the natural gas extracted in oil wells in the Delta is immediately burned or flared into the air at a rate of approximately 70 million m³ per day. This is equivalent to 40% of African natural gas consumption and forms the single largest source of greenhouse gas emissions on the planet. Nigeria also has tar sands, uranium reserves and nearly 1,000 million tons of coal.

Need for a National Energy Policy

The level of energy utilization in an economy, coupled with the efficiency of conversion of energy resources to useful energy, is directly indicative of the level of development of the economy. In order to ensure optimal, adequate, reliable and secure supply of energy to, and its efficient utilization in the country, it is essential to put in place a co-ordinated, coherent and comprehensive energy policy. The policy will serve as a blue print for the sustainable development, supply and utilization of energy resources within the economy, and for the use of such resources in international trade and co-operation.

Hitherto, existing policies in the energy sector have been those of the separate energy sub-sectors, namely, electricity, oil and gas and solid minerals. There had also been energy related policies developed in sub-sectors whose activities are strongly dependent on those in the energy sector. These include transportation, agriculture, science and technology and environment, among others. The sub-sectoral policies, however, reflect the individual sub-sectoral perspectives. It is necessary to have an integrated energy policy, which will guide future energy related sub-sectoral policy developments, in order to avoid policy conflicts which may, otherwise, arise. An overall national energy policy is also normally needed and requested by foreign investors who wish to invest in the nation's economy. In 1984, the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology produced a Draft Energy Policy Guideline. The contents were however limited in scope and depth. The Energy Commission of Nigeria, in furtherance of its mandate, produced a Draft National Energy Policy in 1993. This was later reviewed in 1996 by an Inter-ministerial Committee, under the Chairmanship of the Ministry of Science and Technology. The document was yet to be approved by the Federal Executive Council. In view of significant changes in the orientation of the economy, especially as regards increased private sector participation, it had become necessary to review the 1996 document, prior to its approval. The result of that review by an Inter-ministerial Committee, appointed by Mr. President, is presented in subsequent sections.

Nigerian National Energy Policy

As previously mentioned, the bulk of the actual policies, which the present review evaluates and critiques, emanate from two most recent Nigerian government policy papers; the NEP (Energy Commission of Nigeria 2003) and the NREEP (Ministry of Power 2015). Following highlights of the energy sources and energy utilization trends in the country, the NEP specifically discusses energy issues, energy financing and policy planning and implementation. NEP intends to achieve energy planning and policy implementation through the following strategies:

- ✓ Synchronizing cooperation and communication between the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) and relevant government bodies/institutions in the energy sector.
- ✓ Decentralize energy planning and implementation to the state government level, while simultaneously ensuring consistency with NEP plans.
- ✓ Formation and enforcement of an energy masterplan from updated national energy portfolio by the respective institutions.
- ✓ Aggressively pursue private sector participation in the energy sector.
- ✓ Ensure approval of appropriate fiscal measures to support the energy policy implementation plans.
- ✓ Continuous public awareness and manpower development in the energy services sector.

The NREEEP majorly exists to meet electric power supply targets in a sustainable manner. The main renewable energy sources focused on in the policy are; hydropower, solar (PV and thermal) and wind. Other briefly highlighted sources are; geothermal, wave and tidal energy. Also inculcated in the NREEEP is the national energy efficiency policy framework to complement planned renewable energy policy. Specific focus of the NREEEP can be summarized as;

- Development of more micro (100 kW – 500 kW) and mini (500 kW – 1 MW) hydropower schemes in an environmentally sustainable and socially acceptable manner, with private sector participation. Additional focus was placed on accelerating the completion of Mambila, Zungeru and Gurara large (>100 MW) hydro projects.
 - ✓ 10 % minimum contribution of total electricity generation from hydropower (applying a mix of various scale installations in the power generation).
 - ✓ Use of waste wood (biomass) as an electricity generation source in the mix and other non-wood biomass for alternative off-grid power sources.
 - ✓ Solar PV use as decentralized options for off-grid, remote areas and standalone power applications (1 – 10 kW) like; communications stations and security cameras.
 - ✓ Deployment of concentrated solar power plants (solar thermal) of > 20 MW capacity in applicable locations. Promotion of solar water heating for commercial and industrial processes.

- ✓ Both solar PV and thermal to target a minimum of 3 % and 6% energy generation contribution by 2020 and 2030 respectively.
- ✓ Development of indigenous small-scale wind energy harnessing devices; to be included in the mix in locations where it is technically and economically feasible (percentage target non-specified).
- ✓ Obtaining data, R&D on geothermal, wave and tidal energy resources to encourage exploitation.
- ✓ Finance renewable energy deployment through; budget allocation, privatization of PHCN, fiscal incentives like tax cuts, access to capital market for private investors in renewable and participation of international donors and NGOs.
- ✓ Implementation of feed-in tariffs for certain scale renewable energy deployments. Guaranteed markets and grid connections by local electricity distribution companies, simplified licensing procedure to operators selling < 1 MW.
- ✓ Implementing energy efficiency measures such as demand-side management, promotion of energy saving technologies and tariff provisions for electricity distributions companies that achieve high efficiencies within their customer base.
- ✓ Finance energy efficiency efforts by providing: duty free incentives to imported energy saving equipment for (5 years), 0.5% budget addition to each ministry for purchase or upgrade of energy efficient appliances/equipment and rebates for customers under distribution company who make changes to improve energy efficiency.

Given the limited sites available, continuous development of large-scale HEP is limited for the projections. Therefore, focus is to be on small scale hydro in addition to the other renewables, as the percentage of other renewables (excluding large hydro) in the power supply mix is targeted to increase from 1.3 % to 16 % by 2030.

Energy Policy Overview

The national energy policy recognizes the multi-dimensional nature of energy and therefore addresses diverse issues such as research and development, energy pricing and financing, legislation, energy efficiency, environment etc. The overall thrust of the energy policy is the optimal utilization of the nation's energy resources for sustainable development.

Objectives of Energy Policy

The policy objectives and implementation strategies have been carefully defined with the fundamental guiding premises that energy is crucial to national development goals and that government has a prime role in meeting the energy challenges facing the nation. Furthermore, the dependence on oil can be reduced through the diversification of the nation's energy resources, aggressive research, development and demonstration (R D& D), human resources development, etc. Consequently the overall energy policy objectives may be summarized as follows:

- i. To ensure the development of the nation's energy resources, with diversified energy resources option, for the achievement of national energy security and an efficient energy delivery system with an optimal energy resource mix.
- ii. To guarantee increased contribution of energy productive activities to national income.
- iii. To guarantee adequate, reliable and sustainable supply of energy at appropriate costs and in an environmentally friendly manner, to the various sectors of the economy, for national development.
- iv. To guarantee an efficient and cost effective consumption pattern of energy resources.
- v. To accelerate the process of acquisition and diffusion of technology and managerial expertise in the energy sector and indigenous participation in energy sector industries, for stability and self-reliance.
- vi. To promote increased investments and development of the energy sector industries with substantial private sector participation.

- vii. To ensure a comprehensive, integrated and well informed energy sector plans and programs for effective development.
- viii. To foster international co-operation in energy trade and projects development in both the African region and the world at large. To successfully use the nation's abundant energy resources to promote international co-operation.

Energy and Natural Resources Policy; A Review

Nigeria has made considerable efforts to establish an effective energy system, resulting in significant growth within the country's energy sector (Akinlo, 2012). Internationally, Nigeria has actively participated in global initiatives aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions. These include its involvement in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (1994), the Kyoto Protocol (2004), the Copenhagen and Cancun Agreements (2010), the Durban Platform for Enhanced Action (2011), and the Paris Agreement (FGN, 2015). At the regional level, Nigeria is a key participant in the West African Power Pool (WAPP), which aims to create a unified regional electricity market that ensures a stable, reliable, and cost-effective electricity supply (WAPP, 2018). Domestically, the country has implemented numerous transitions through a range of programs, policies, and initiatives within the local energy sector (Gungah et al., 2019). However, Bamgbopa et al. (2019) critique Nigeria's energy policy as represented in two key national policy documents: the National Energy Policy (NEP) (Energy Commission of Nigeria, 2003) and the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) (Ministry of Power, 2015). Their analysis found that while these policies are largely adequate—addressing many of the necessary areas—there remains a need for continued attention and amendment. In particular, they emphasize the importance of expanding electric capacity with a growing share of renewables, enhancing local oil refining capacity, improving gas gathering and management, and eliminating gas flaring. Despite these efforts, Nigeria's energy sector continues to face substantial challenges, which have affected access to renewable energy across the country.

Energy access is widely recognized as a fundamental prerequisite for tackling major global challenges of the 21st century. It has gained renewed focus with the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDG 7, which aims to "ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all" (UNEP, 2017; Mathew et al., 2018; Nalule, 2019). Thus, it is not an overstatement to hypothesize that energy access, or the establishment of an effective energy system, significantly enhances a nation's prospects for achieving sustainable development. Ultimately, access to energy serves as a catalyst for development (Pachauri, 2011) and is essential for improving quality of life (Mupunga, 2011), thereby contributing to longterm sustainable development. Over the past two decades, the growing demand for energy has compelled many Sub-Saharan African countries, including the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ghana, and Nigeria, to diversify investments into various energy sources to meet rising needs (Carli et al., 2018). In this context, renewable energy has emerged as the most viable option to meet energy demands at global, regional, and national levels (Emodi and Ebele, 2016; Jurasz et al., 2020). Debates around the concept of renewable energy date back to the early 20th century. Some scholars used the term in contrast to finite fossil fuel resources (Bell, 1906; Clarke et al., 1909), while others sought to distinguish between "renewable" and "inexhaustible" energy sources—categorizing draught animals and fuelwood as renewable, and solar, wind, tidal, and hydro energy as inexhaustible (Clarke et al., 1909, cited in Harjanne and Korhonen, 2019). The International Energy Agency (IEA) defines renewable energy as "energy derived from natural processes that are replenished at a faster rate than they are consumed" (IEA, 2019). These sources include solar, hydro, wind, biomass, geothermal, and marine energy. Renewable energy is also referred to as green energy (Chakraborty and Mazzanti, 2020; Bucur and Bucur, 2020), clean energy (IEA, 2019; Somorin et al., 2019; Berry, 2020), or non-conventional energy. It is widely regarded as a key solution to global climate challenges (Harjanne and Korhonen, 2019). While it is important to note that renewable energy is not entirely without environmental impact (Abbasi and Abbasi, 2000), it generally causes far less harm than fossil fuels and contributes positively to economic growth.

Consequently, many countries are increasingly exploring new development pathways that incorporate renewable energy as a core component of sustainable development strategies. In response, policy scholars have explored how theories, models, and frameworks can be applied to improve policy processes and outcomes, particularly in the context of renewable energy systems (Ruseva et al., 2019). Developing effective renewable energy policy requires assessing the legal, regulatory, and economic frameworks necessary to support renewable energy capacity (Chapman, McLellan, and Tezuka, 2016). However, this process often faces challenges, especially among policy designers. This is due to the fact that many tools used to achieve renewable energy policy goals are economically driven—encompassing investment costs, pricing mechanisms, tax incentives, depreciation allowances, and monetary penalties for non-compliance (Chapman et al., 2016). Drawing from the SDGs, it is evident that the energy system is directly linked to sustainable development goals and constitutes a major focus under SDG 7. This underscores the need to understand how renewable energy policy impacts sustainable development. While the relationship between renewable energy and economic growth has yielded mixed results in the literature, findings range from positive effects (Alege et al., 2019) to negative (Ocal and Aslan, 2013; Astariz and Iglesias, 2015), and in some cases, statistically insignificant outcomes (Tugcu and Tiwari, 2016; Schilling and Esmundo, 2009). In terms of sustainable development, Moe (2005) argues that achieving this goal—particularly through renewable energy policy—must be considered within the framework of its three core pillars: economic, social, and environmental dimensions. According to Brightest (2024), true sustainable development is achieved only when these three pillars are in harmony.

Building on numerous studies that suggest not only renewable energy systems but also renewable energy policy can significantly influence a nation's sustainable development, it is crucial to examine the specific impact of renewable energy policy on sustainability outcomes. Edomah et al. (2016) investigated the linkages and consequences of policy decisionmaking in the governance of energy infrastructure in Nigeria. Their findings highlight the critical role of policymakers in driving development outcomes within the country.

Romano (2015) conducted an analysis of the impact of competition policy on economic growth using a panel data model based on a sample of 138 countries from 2009 to 2013. The study demonstrated a direct relationship between the effectiveness of competition policy and changes in real GDP per capita, providing empirical evidence of the positive effects of policy enforcement on macroeconomic performance. Similarly, Salman (2016) examined the relationship between policy frameworks and economic growth, focusing particularly on policies that foster entrepreneurial activities. The study found that policies which support entrepreneurship significantly contribute to accelerating economic development. This occurs through various policy instruments, including investment in education, support for research and development, favourable tax policies, and stable monetary policy. Hence, this may have a significant impact on the achievement of sustainable development. Accordingly, this article focuses on evaluating renewable energy policymaking and its potential impact on sustainable development in Nigeria.

Energy Security Challenges in Nigeria

Despite being a major player in the global oil industry, Nigeria's energy sector is plagued with inefficiencies and setbacks, according to Orazulike's (2012) study. These issues affect the energy security of the nation, and Orazulike investigates the individual challenges faced by different energy resources in Nigeria. One of these resources, diesel, is troubled by the inefficiency of both the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) and National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) in supplying electricity to individuals and businesses. This has led citizens to rely on diesel as an alternative source of power, but the high demand for diesel has made its availability and pricing a major issue in Nigeria. Petrol, which is the most controversial energy resource in Nigeria, has also been plagued with inefficiency as its security is controlled by a group of elites known as cabals, who make decisions regarding petrol based on their own interests. The challenges facing Nigeria's energy sector are numerous and complex. Despite being a major security is hampered by inefficiencies and corruption across various sectors. Orazulike (2012) highlighted the challenges faced by different energy resources in Nigeria. Diesel, for instance, is relied

upon by individuals and businesses as an alternative source of electricity due to the inefficiency of the country's power distribution companies. This heavy reliance on diesel has led to an increase in demand for the resource, but its availability and pricing remain major issues in the country. Petrol, Nigeria's most controversial energy resource, is also marred by inefficiencies and corruption. The security of petrol as a resource is in the hands of a small group of elites who make decisions regarding its distribution in their own interests, rather than the interests of the general public. The natural gas sector has similarly been affected by availability and affordability issues that discourage average citizens from demanding Liquefied Natural Gas. Kerosene supply has been controlled by major middlemen and unlicensed personnel in the petroleum sector, resulting in increased prices for consumers. Other challenges include corruption tendencies that hinder the implementation of effective policies, insecurity, and external forces that negatively impact energy security.

Nigeria's mono-cultural system has encouraged a heavy dependency on oil and gas, with the country's budget tied closely to fluctuations in oil prices. Environmental pollution in the energy zone has also led to social unrest in the oil regions, with political effects manifesting in the form of vandalism, kidnapping, trade unionism, and cartels in oil and gas. The inefficiency of the nation's refinery capacity has further compounded these issues. The refineries available are underutilized, which means there is a looming threat of resource importation, even for Nigeria's own resources. This situation has led to fuel shortages, parallel market activities, and increased prices. Adenikinju (2010) noted that this has put the nation in a state of economic disequilibrium, with the energy sector being a significant contributor to the overall instability of the Nigerian economy.

Challenges of Renewable Energy Policy on Sustainable Development

Adedipe et al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive study on Nigeria's onshore wind energy potential, assessing the suitability of various geographic zones for wind power generation. The study concluded that Nigeria's wind energy sector remains underdeveloped, largely due to inadequate research and technological capacity, insufficient government support for wind energy initiatives, and challenges related to land ownership and acquisition. Similarly, Somorin et al. (2017) noted that Nigeria's over-reliance on hydropower—subject to seasonal water level fluctuations—has been a significant barrier to the effective deployment of other renewable energy systems. This issue highlights the urgent need for policymakers to implement robust and inclusive renewable energy policies that address energy demand and supply as part of a broader strategy for achieving sustainable development. Onyekwelu (2021) also identified the abandonment of projects and the lack of emphasis on wind energy within Nigeria's renewable energy policy framework as major impediments. Compared to other renewable energy sources, wind energy has received limited policy attention, undermining its potential contribution to energy sustainability and, by extension, national sustainable development goals. Bello et al. (2019) further observed that the absence of policies supporting the effective application of technology in renewable energy systems hinders the long-term sustainability of energy resources, thereby negatively impacting efforts to achieve sustainable development. Chinedu (2025), in his re-examination of renewable energy development in Nigeria, highlighted several persistent challenges. These include regulatory bottlenecks, high capital costs, technical capacity gaps, and market distortions caused by fossil fuel subsidies—all of which constrain the use of policy as a tool for transforming Nigeria's renewable energy system to support the achievement of sustainable development goals. The findings from Somorin et al. (2017), Adedipe et al. (2018), Onyekwelu (2021), and Chinedu (2025) collectively reveal that a range of challenges continue to undermine the effective implementation of renewable energy policies in Nigeria. These obstacles limit the capacity of the country's renewable energy system to significantly contribute to sustainable development. Energypedia (2025) reviewed key challenges and opportunities within Nigeria's energy sector and outlined the primary challenges that impede effective policy decision-making and the development of renewable energy systems. These challenges include:

- i. Funding constraints, as the renewable energy sector is solely financed by the Federal Government, which lacks adequate resources to meet all policy and investment needs.

- ii. Inadequate geographical coverage, as current policies fail to address energy needs in many parts of the country.
- iii. Outdated policies with inadequate provisions for redundancy and flexibility.
- iv. Insufficient financial resources to expand, modernize, and maintain energy infrastructure.
- v. Inadequate policy frameworks for integrating new technologies to enhance energy delivery.
- vi. Failure to prioritize urgent maintenance of energy systems when needed.
- vii. Delays in the implementation of new policies and renewable energy projects.
- viii. A lack of sustained and effective collaboration between the Federal Government and external stakeholders, including Independent Power Producers (IPP) and joint venture (JV) international oil companies.

Theoretical Underpinning of the Administration of Energy Resources and Systems

Several challenges exist in managing the reliability, operation, control, and administration of energy resources and systems (Sao & Lehn, 2008; Barghi Latran et al., 2015). The application of game theory has gained significant attention as a means of addressing these challenges by providing effective solutions for decision-making and control processes, particularly in the energy sector (Singh, 2006; Mannini, Eynard, & Grieu, 2022). Game theory serves as a crucial analytical tool for studying and understanding strategic interactions, particularly in the context of rational decision-making (Yarar, Yoldas, Bahceci, Onen, & Jung, 2024). According to this theory, all participants and actors are assumed to be rational, with their decisions influenced by the choices of others. Game theory contributes to the development of systematic approaches to logical decision-making, particularly in the energy sector (Yarar et al., 2024). The application of game theory in energy and power systems dates back to the 1970s, and its use has since expanded, particularly for analyzing and understanding energy systems (Yarar et al., 2024). Haitao (2022) emphasized that game theory plays a crucial role in understanding effective policy decision-making in the renewable energy sector, as it aids in protecting the natural environment, improving human living standards, and generating economic benefits in various ways. Furthermore, the Ecology of Games Theory (EGT) conceptualizes policy processes as complex adaptive systems (Folke et al., 2005; Levin, 1998; Lavin et al., 2002) and serves as a theoretical framework for analyzing polycentric governance systems (Berardo & Lubell, 2016).

EGT builds on sociological policy process theories to explain how networks of policy actors—such as those involved in ensuring sustainability within Nigeria’s energy system— shape policy strategies (Lubell, 2013). This approach provides a method for analyzing the design, outputs, and outcomes of collaborative policymaking in domains with overlapping stakeholders and issues (Ruseva et al., 2019), making it particularly relevant for achieving a sustainable energy system in Nigeria. Thus, in examining the challenges and opportunities associated with renewable energy systems for effective policymaking in Nigeria, game theory offers valuable insights into how policy actors can influence policymaking strategies. This, in turn, can facilitate the development of policies that enhance energy resource efficiency, boost economic growth, reduce poverty, and improve overall well-being in the country.

Key Findings of the Study

The findings of the study revealed that:

1. With regard to the status and sources of energy use in Nigeria, the study found out that energy is the most fundamental part of our universe as it lights our cities, power our vehicles, transport planes and rockets, warms our homes, cook our food, play our music and powers machinery in factories. The study equally revealed that the available energy resources in Nigeria include hydrocarbons such as oil, gas, coal and uranium, renewable energy such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, biomass and geothermal as well as nuclear energy as an alternative source of electricity. The study observed that, the primary sources of energy can be grouped into two: Renewable energy which is an energy source that we can use and replenish. Example include sun (solar energy), wind (wind energy), earth (geothermal energy), biological waste (biomass energy), and water (hydropower). While non-renewable energy is the conventional source of

energy, which we cannot replace as we use - it cannot be renewed. Non-renewable sources include fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas and coal.

2. The study further found out with regards to the need for a national energy policy observed that, in order to ensure optimal, adequate, reliable and secure supply of energy to, and its efficient utilization in the country, it is essential to put in place a co-ordinated, coherent and comprehensive energy policy. The finding equally noted that, the policy will serve as a blue print for the sustainable development, supply and utilization of energy resources within the economy, and for the use of such resources in international trade and co-operation.
3. Subsequently, the study found out with respect to energy security challenges in Nigeria posits that despite being a major player in the global oil industry, Nigeria's energy sector is plagued with inefficiencies and setbacks. This finding is in consonant with the study of Orazulike's (2012), where he investigates the individual challenges faced by different energy resources in Nigeria. For instance, he noted that diesel as a resources, is troubled by the inefficiency of both the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) and National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) in supplying electricity to individuals and businesses. Also the study found out that petrol, which is the most controversial energy resource in Nigeria, has also been plagued with inefficiency as its security is controlled by a group of elites known as cabals, who make decisions regarding petrol based on their own interests.
4. Conversely, on the issue of the challenges of renewable energy policy on sustainable development, the study found out that, Adedipe et al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive study on Nigeria's onshore wind energy potential, assessing the suitability of various geographic zones for wind power generation. This study concluded that Nigeria's wind energy sector remains underdeveloped, largely due to inadequate research and technological capacity, insufficient government support for wind energy initiatives, and challenges related to land ownership and acquisition. Similarly, the observed with regards to Somorin et al. (2017) noted that Nigeria's over-reliance on hydropower—subject to seasonal water level fluctuations—has been a significant barrier to the effective deployment of other renewable energy systems. More so, Onyekwelu (2021) also identified the abandonment of projects and the lack of emphasis on wind energy within Nigeria's renewable energy policy framework as major impediments.
5. The finding of the study with regards to the theoretical underpinning of the administration of energy resources and systems noted for instance that, the game theory serves as a crucial analytical tool for studying and understanding strategic interactions, particularly in the context of rational decision-making (Yarar, Yoldas, Bahceci, Onen, & Jung, 2024). According to this theory, all participants and actors are assumed to be rational, with their decisions influenced by the choices of others. Conversely, the study equally found out that, the Ecological Game Theory (EGT) which is a sociological policy process theory explain how networks of policy actors—such as those involved in ensuring sustainability within Nigeria's energy system— shape policy strategies (Lubell, 2013). This approach according to Ruseva et al., (2019) provides a method for analyzing the design, outputs, and outcomes of collaborative policymaking in domains with overlapping stakeholders and issues, making it particularly relevant for achieving a sustainable energy system in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this study archival research was conducted. Archival research can be used in various fields for building a reliable knowledge base (Tranfield et al., 2003). For the purpose of this term paper, archival research was adopted to provide insight on existing literatures and empirical studies by congregating available research studies. A literature review of past ten years research (2015 to 2025) was conducted using search engines such as EBSCO, PROQUEST, JSTOR and Google Scholar and we drew our inferences from aggregating the results of previous researches.

CONCLUSION

Our discussions have revealed that the Energy sector of Nigeria remains the corner stone of the entire economy, it has revealed that the existing policy needs to be adjusted to fit into the global trend. It was also revealed that renewable energy has been greatly neglected. In conclusion, Nigeria possesses abundant and promising renewable energy resources, including solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. Additionally, several opportunities exist for enhancing the country's renewable energy sector, such as potential legislative reforms, institutional strengthening, financial incentives, and the promotion of technological innovation and infrastructure development. Furthermore, various policies have been established to support the effective utilization of renewable energy in Nigeria, including the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP), the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA) of 2005, the National Energy Policy (2003), and the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) of 2021, among others. Nevertheless, several challenges continue to hinder progress in the sector. These include the absence of a comprehensive and coherent energy policy, the lack of energy efficiency programs, ineffective policy implementation, regulatory burdens, investor uncertainty, legal and regulatory inconsistencies, institutional inefficiencies, financial constraints, and technical challenges. Addressing these challenges through the establishment of a well-structured and enhanced policy framework is essential for advancing Nigeria's renewable energy sector. Given the country's abundant renewable energy resources, the implementation of effective policies is crucial to ensuring the development of a sustainable and efficient renewable energy system in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The government and policymakers should establish a clear and comprehensive policy and regulatory framework to support the development of energy and renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal energy.
- ii. The government should increase Nigeria's energy targets and ambitions to unlock low-carbon growth and align with global climate and sustainable development objectives.
- iii. There is a need to invest in renewable energy infrastructure, including transmission and distribution networks, to facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources into the national grid.
- iv. The government and policymakers should enhance public awareness and education on the benefits of renewable energy to promote adoption and increase support for renewable energy policies.
- v. The government should implement fiscal policies such as tax incentives and carbon pricing mechanisms to provide financial incentives for transitioning to renewable energy sources.
- vi. The government and policymakers should introduce regulatory policies such as: Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS), requiring utilities to generate a specified percentage of electricity from renewable energy sources. Net Metering, enabling households and businesses to generate their own renewable energy and sell excess energy to the grid. Grid Connection Policies, streamlining the process of connecting renewable energy projects to the grid by reducing bureaucratic hurdles and associated costs.
- vii. The establishment of a dedicated renewable energy agency is recommended to oversee the sector's development and provide support to stakeholders.
- viii. The government should introduce education and training programs for renewable energy professionals, including technicians, engineers, and project developers. Public awareness campaigns should be launched to educate citizens on the benefits of renewable energy and promote adoption. Moreover, renewable energy concepts should be integrated into school curricula to prepare the next generation of professionals and leaders.
- ix. The government should foster international collaborations, climate change agreements, and regional cooperation. Partnering with organizations such as the Economic Community of

West African States (ECOWAS) can enhance regional renewable energy development and knowledge sharing.

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